

A STUDY ON LINK BETWEEN EQUAL EMPLOYMENT OPPORTUNITY AND DIVERSITY IN THE WORKPLACE IN GIG ECONOMY

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Abstract:

The gig economy has been a driving force in shaping the future of work. In the present research primary data were collected by structured questionnaire from 100 respondents in Coimbatore district. The main objectivity of the study was to study the conceptual framework of equal employment opportunity and analyze the factors influencing the diversity in the workplace. The collected data was analyzed using simple percentage, standard deviation and rotated component matrix. The study concludes that with the rising costs and large millions seeking employment, a gig economy opens doors to earning fresh income through gig work.

Key Words: Economy, Employment, Driving, Opportunities, Diversity, Gig, Economy, Etc.,

Introduction:

The gig economy has been a driving force in shaping the future of work. Its specific of unique employment relationship upends the traditional ways of working in numerous ways; since there's no employer-hand relationship, the gig workers aren't bounden to any particular employer and thus have lesser inflexibility in terms of the work they can choose and the hours they devote. Businesses enjoy analogous inflexibility when they aren't dependent on a set of workers for executing tasks, and also profit from avoiding the cost of social security and fixed remuneration that are handed to an hand. Still, gig economy has invited praise and wrath in equal measures. Although it seems like a palm- palm situation for both parties, the ground reality is frequently more complicated.

Over the times, the growing fashion ability of platform businesses has been accompanied with pockets of kick by their workers primarily those engaged in hack and delivery services from time to time. In India, the grievances have substantially been related to remuneration and the working conditions. (i) According to gig workers in India, the low payment frequently pushes them to work longer than 8 hours, and work on all days of the week. (ii) Still, it's the veritably model of gig economy that exposes the workers to similar vulnerabilities, as a business cannot be held responsible if the workers aren't workers. This raises questions about the ethical base of the gig economy, and necessitates a farther study of its overall structure.

Originally, one needs to draw a distinction between gig economy and platform businesses. As per the World Economic Forum, gig economy is defined by its focus on pool participation and income generation via "gigs", single systems or tasks for which a worker is hired. On the other hand, platform businesses serve as commerce where merchandisers and buyers can be matched.

Platform- enabled gig workers can be categorized into high-professed gig workers and low-professed gig workers. Besides the different position of chops offered by the two, a major difference is that high-professed workers are smaller in force than low-professed gig workers, and therefore have lesser logrolling power than the ultimate in the labor request. This is why issues of gig economy are concentrated to low-professed or blue-collar gig workers, and when questions about the gig economy are raised, the questions about the gig economy are raised, the questions are actually about the part of it that caters to the blue- collar workers.

The gig economy in the abecedarian sense offers a work arrangement that works for everyone involved, but it's when the power dynamics come into the equation that the delicate balance is thrown off. From the perspective of a worker, being an hand entails further severity of working hours and pay, whereas the gig economy has further options of work assignments and payment immolations to choose from, further inflexibility of working hours and lesser freedom of switching from task to task. Still, when the labor force is high and more disposable, as in the case of blue- collar workers, the gig workers have no power to impact payment immolations, and freedom to choose becomes but an vision. In the interplay of demand and force mechanisms, the gig workers always lose out. Therefore, as platforms come more popular among gig workers, further of them join the pool, therefore driving down their own remuneration.

Nonetheless, the gig economy still has a lot to offer. In a country like India where informal working arrangements dominate the economy, numerous blue- collar workers formerly work in precarious conditions, face income instability and have no employment stability. In comparison, gig economy is a better volition. Besides having a system in place that's fairer than informal work arrangements, it's also characterized by ease of entry. The informal network in the informal economy that may produce walls of entry for outlanders doesn't live

in the gig economy. Gig work has also been a source of supplementary income for those facing profitable rigors, and tided them over until they could find employment openings. For the Indian economy as well, the gig economy has been responsible for a huge proportion of job creation, which is only projected to increase in the coming times.

Review of Literature:

Ruth (2012) in his article entitled “Why Diversity Really Matters?” discusses the inequality in New Zealand which predominately exists in the recruitment process. The article throws light at the hurdles confronted via way of means of the migrants in searching for jobs in New Zealand. The foremost regions of demanding situations to migrants which includes the troubles in speaking in English, problems confronted in consumer interplay and agreement problems have been discussed. The article presents perspectives on gender and incapacity discrimination. In addition to this, the object presents guidelines to address the variety successfully. Equal employment possibility works throughout diverse age groups, gender, ethnicity and special backgrounds and additionally guide commercial enterprise human beings in growing businesses of more variety.

Jindal, Bagade and Sharma, (2013) in their study entitled, “Impact of work force diversity on work culture of Indian organizations” discussed the importance of diversity since globalization highlights the blessings of using various staff in businesses and discusses its effect on Indian way of life and Indian businesses. The take a look at highlights at the reality that which will shine nicely with inside the international marketplace and to have a aggressive side over different businesses within side the world, the Indian businesses have to consciousness on adopting techniques and techniques to efficaciously manipulate diversity.

Samardzic and Gregson, (2011) in their study entitled, “Commitment or Even Compliance? An Australian University’s Approach to Equal Employment Opportunity” highlights the difficulties faced by female gender in their career path in the field of academics. The study revealed that university as a case study. This study highlight on the approaches that can be implemented to overcome these difficulties and the policies of equal employment opportunity in the university. The study revealed that promotion procedures were mostly not concerned with gender equality rather it was mainly a male dominated model which was taking place for the criteria for promotions.

Aarathi and Manivannan, (2016) in their study entitled, “A study on gender discrimination in the workplace” revealed the issues faced by women employees arising out of sex inequality in the organizations. The study examined the factors causing gender discrimination in information technology organizations. The study founded that first-hand information was obtained from three hundred and twenty employees working in IT companies and suggestions that were provided to promote gender equality in the workplace.

Objectives:

- To study the conceptual framework of equal employment opportunity in the workplace.
- To analyze the factors influencing the diversity in the workplace.

Limitations of the Study:

- The study is restricted to the selected sample from Coimbatore District and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.
- The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Research Methodology:

- Area of study: The research study was done in Coimbatore
- Nature and source of data: The study is based on primary data; primary data has been collected from various respondents in Coimbatore using questionnaire method and the secondary data have been collected from related websites, journals, magazines, internet and textbooks. A sample of 100 respondents was selected for the study.

Statistical Tools Used for Study:

- Simple percentage
- Standard Deviation
- Rotated Component Matrix

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Gender and Level of Equal Employment Opportunity in the Workplace

S.No	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage%	Average	Range		Standard Deviation
					Min	Max	
1	Male	44	44	24.21	10	46	7.848
2	Female	56	56	23.9	10	46	7.209
	Total		100	24.04	10	46	7.497

Source: Primary data

It could be noted from the above table that the level of equal employment opportunity in the workplace in gig economy among the male respondents ranged between 10 and 46 with an average of 24.21. The level of

equal employment opportunity in the workplace among the female respondents ranged between 10 and 46 with an average of 23.90. Hence, it is inferred from the analysis that the equal employment opportunity in the workplace in gig economy was at the maximum level among the respondents who were male.

Table 2: Age and Level of Equal Employment Opportunity in the Workplace

S.No	Age in Years	No. of Respondents	Percentage %	Average	Range		Standard Deviation
					Min	Max	
1	Below 30	62	62	24.33	10	46	7.704
2	31 – 50	36	36	23.53	10	44	7.127
3	Above 50	2	2	25.8	15	31	7.43
	Total	100	100	24.04	10	46	7.497

Source: Primary data

It could be noted from the above table that the level of equal employment opportunity in the workplace in gig economy among the respondents who belonged to the age group of below 30 years ranged between 10 and 46 with an average of 24.33. The level of equal employment opportunity in the workplace among the respondents who belonged to the age group between 31 and 50 years ranged between 10 and 44 with an average of 23.53 whereas for the respondents who belonged to the age group of above 50 years, it ranged between 15 and 31 with an average of 25.8. Hence, it is inferred from the analysis that the equal employment opportunity in the workplace was at the maximum level among the respondents who belonged to the age group of above 50 years.

Table 3: Marital Status and Level of Equal Employment Opportunity in the Workplace

S.No	Marital Status	No. of Respondents	Percentage %	Average	Range		Standard Deviation
					Min	Max	
1	Married	57	57	23.84	10	44	6.9
2	Unmarried	43	43	24.3	10	46	8.215
	Total	100	100	24.04	10	46	7.497

Source: Primary data

It could be noted from the above table that the level of equal employment opportunity in the workplace among the married respondents ranged between 10 and 44 with an average of 23.84. The level of equal employment opportunity in the workplace among the unmarried respondents ranged between 10 and 46 with an average of 24.30. Hence, it is inferred from the analysis that the equal employment opportunity in the workplace was at the maximum level among the respondents who were unmarried.

Table 4: Educational Qualification and Level of Equal Employment Opportunity in the Workplace

S.No	Educational Qualification	No. of Respondents	Percentage %	Average	Range		Standard Deviation
					Min	Max	
1	Under Graduate	49	49	24.43	10	46	7.79
2	Post Graduate	45	45	23.34	10	46	7.13
3	Professionals	4	4	26.26	10	38	6.904
4	Others	2	2	26.78	19	40	8.585
	Total	100	100	24.04	10	46	7.497

Source: Primary data

It could be noted from the above table that the level of equal employment opportunity in the workplace in gig economy among the respondents who were under graduates ranged between 10 and 46 with an average of 24.43. The level of equal employment opportunity in the workplace among the respondents who were holding post degrees ranged between 10 and 46 with an average of 23.34 whereas for the respondents who were holding Professionals , it ranged between 10 and 38 with an average of 26.26. The level of equal employment opportunity among the respondents who belonged to others category ranged between 19 and 40 with an average of 26.78. Hence, it is inferred from the analysis that the equal employment opportunity in the workplace in Tamil Nadu was at the maximum level among the respondents who belonged to others category.

Table 5: Salary and Level of Equal Employment Opportunity in the Workplace

S.No	Salary in Rupees per month	No. of Respondents	Percentage %	Average	Range		Standard Deviation
					Min	Max	
1	Less than 25,000	27	27	24.4	10	44	7.744
2	25,000 – 50,000	48	48	23.93	10	44	7.236
3	Above 50,000	25	25	23.87	10	46	7.734
	Total	100	100	24.04	10	46	7.497

Source: Primary data

It could be noted from the above table that the level of equal employment opportunity and diversity in the workplace in gig economy among the respondents who had a monthly salary of less than Rs.25000 ranged between 10 and 44 with an average of 24.40. The level of equal employment opportunity and diversity in the workplace among the respondents who had a monthly salary of Rs.25000 to Rs.50000 ranged between 10 and

44 with an average of 23.93 Whereas for the respondents who had a monthly salary of more than Rs.50000, it ranged between 10 and 46 with an average of 23.87. Hence, it is inferred from the analysis that the equal employment opportunity and diversity in the workplace was at themaximum

Table 6: Diversity in Workplace Rotated Component Matrix

Variables	Component		
	1	2	3
Workload partiality	0.389	0.341	0.666
Biased attitude	0.348	0.289	0.697
Special privilege for women employees	0.124	0.082	0.781
Male employee is getting more salary than female employee for the same work	0.786	0.277	0.030
Male employees are getting promotion faster than female employees	0.759	0.222	0.121
Offering workers different wages based on their sex/gender.	0.809	0.157	0.131
A superior offering more attention and instruction to one sex/gender	0.645	-0.070	0.496
Only hiring people of a certain sex/gender for a specific type of job	0.692	0.035	0.411
Selecting workers for redundancy or pay cuts because of sex/gender	0.782	0.097	0.257
Not promoting or offering a pay rise to a worker because of that person's sex/gender	0.739	0.250	0.170
Women, if they are given the top leader position cannot handle power	0.551	0.165	0.321
Women employees are generally not assigned 'safe/risky jobs in companies where they are employed	0.629	0.023	0.391
Recipient of unwanted physical contact at work	0.480	0.583	0.010
Items of a sexual nature (pictures, posters, etc) have ever been displayed in your work	0.191	0.832	0.093
Recipient of unwanted leer, sexual comments, noises or gestures in your workplace	0.168	0.839	0.152
You have ever received text messages or emails at work, which are sexual in nature	0.110	0.836	0.121
You have ever been "rated" based on looks or sexuality in your workplace	0.021	0.787	0.143

From table 6, the variable Workload partiality has the highest factor loading of 0.666 in the third element. Also, the variables Prejudiced station and Special honor for women workers “ have the highest factor loading of 0.697 and 0.781 independently in the third element. The variables Manly hand is getting further payment than womanish hand for the same work, Manly workers are getting creation briskly than womanish workers,

Offering workers different stipend grounded on their coitus/ gender, A superior immolation further attention and instruction to one coitus/ gender, Only hiring people of a certain coitus/ gender for a specific type of job, Opting workers for redundancy or pay cuts because of coitus/ gender, Not promoting or offering a pay rise to a worker because of that person's coitus/ gender,

Women, if they're given the top leader position cannot handle power and women workers are generally not assigned' safe/ parlous jobs in companies where they're employed “ have the highest factor loading of 0.786, 0.759, 0.809, 0.645, 0.692, 0.782, 0.739, 0.551 and 0.629 independently in the first element.

From the rotated factor loadings, the statements are reduced to three factors and these uprooted factors are named depending upon the variables included under each factor.

Conclusion:

Gig economy allows task power, convenience and inflexibility. Grounded on tastes and preferences, you can determine the number and type of systems you work on, the amount of individual earnings, and therefore, the work- life balance. Individuals have the freedom to not offer your services for a task if you don't believe in the underpinning cause of the task – a inflexibility you don't have in a traditional job. An increase in the relinquishment of smart phones and the rate of digitization is enabling gig freelancers to offer colorful professional services through tech- grounded platforms. Gig workers can subscribe up for tasks in which they're more professed. For illustration – performing interior decoration on a freelance base for multiple consumers rather of bearing a full- time innards designing job at a commercial. With the rising costs and large millions seeking employment, a gig economy opens doors to earning fresh income through gig work. A rise in the education position and tech- knowledge position is farther empowering this economy of the future.

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